

QUIZ

LAST NAME: NYAMALI

FIRST NAME: CHARLES

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INSTRUCTOR: CLEENEWERCK

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ QUESTIONS

1. Which of the following are two common forms of citation in research?

- Bibliography and Notes-bibliography styles
- Parenthetical and Author-date styles
- Notes-bibliography and Author-date style¹**
- Author-bibliography and Notes-parenthetical styles

2. What is plagiarism?

- Using a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information²**
- A general principle based on our experience in the world that is used to support our claims in an argument
- A personal opinion that is used to support an argument
- When details are irrelevant or a source is not important enough to warrant more space

¹ Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 87.

² EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 9.

3. Which of the following is not a type of question researchers usually seek to answer?

- Practical questions: what should we do?
- Theoretical questions: what must we practice to know what to do?**³
- Applied questions: what must we understand before we know what to do?
- Conceptual questions: what should we think?

4. Which of the following is an appropriate reason to quote directly from a source material?

- The quoted words are not from an authority and the views expressed do not back up your views
- The quoted words are strikingly not original
- A passage states a view that you disagree with and to be fair, you want to state it exactly**⁴
- The quoted words do not express your key concepts

5. What is a signal phrase?

- A phrase that comes after a quotation
- A phrase that introduces a quotation**⁵
- A phrase that is within a quotation
- A quotation that is a phrase

³ Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16-17.

⁴Ibid., 49.

⁵ EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 32.

6. What is a style guide?

- An approach a writer uses to phrase a quotation
- A phrase that is styled as a quotation
- A means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that needs to be consistent⁶**
- A quotation approach to ensure a write style

7. The Acquis in the European Union (EU) refers to:

- The body of EU law in the broad sense⁷**
- A general guide to the governance of the EU
- A standing committee in the EU
- An arm of the governing council of the EU

8. The European Investment Fund is an institution whose main objective is:

- Guaranteeing loans for investment projects
- To support the creation, growth and development of small and medium-sized enterprises⁸**
- To maintain the purchasing power and price stability in the euro area
- To support projects designed to improve the environment and develop transport infrastructure

⁶ EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 52.

⁷ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. 2011. English Style Guide, *A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Revised Dec. 2011, 51.

⁸ Ibid., 68.

9. A research proposal is:

- A document used in business to solicit for contracts
- A research document presenting the findings of a research
- An action plan for the presentation of business ideas
- A well-thought-out written action plan.../ working document on the way to the production of a dissertation⁹**

10. A conceptual framework is:

- A conceptual question
- When you quote from sources that are generally known and accepted
- An argument that defines the research
- A working tool that guides the entire research study¹⁰**

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⁹ Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. 2008. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. 1st ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc, 18.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, xxiii.